

Determination of some trace elements in cement and cement raw materials by atomic absorption spectrometry

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The trace elements in cement, raw materials, the precipitator dust and some additive materials, such as gypsum and slag, which are added for improving some physical properties of the cement have been determined by flame atomic absorption spectrophotometry.

Law *et al.*¹ have used a new fusion agent (lithium tetraborate-lithium carbonate and oxalic acid) for the rapid analysis of cement and cement raw meal using atomic absorption spectroscopy (AAS). In the present work, this fusion agent has been used for the analysis of cement, raw meals, gypsum, electrostatic precipitator dust and slag using AAS technique. The method has been successfully extended to determine Cu, Cr, Pb, Zn, Ni, Co, Sr and Cd in the samples.

Results and discussion

The sodium carbonate-lithium tetraborate fusion system is efficient to convert silica in a soluble form². Lithium carbonate was chosen because of its lower melting point so that fusion can be carried out at a lower temperature. Although lithium tetraborate is expensive, it was chosen for it can convert silica into soluble form. Lithium tetraborate is preferable to lithium metaborate because of its preferential purity. Oxalic acid shortens the dissolution time.

Law *et al.*¹ found the appropriate ratio of lithium tetraborate, lithium carbonate and oxalic acid as 1 : 1 : 1, which gave the best recoveries. Further, the dissolution time was shortened from 30 to nearly 10 min. Also, no precipitation of silicon was observed and hence a better recovery was obtained.

The average contents of trace elements in cement and other materials are shown in Table 1. These results are the averages of the contents given by the Unicam and GBC apparatus which give results nearly the same.

The least quantity of heavy metals was found in carbo-

naceous rocks. Clays are more enriched in trace elements. The trace elements in these raw materials agree with the distribution of the metals in the earth's crust especially for the silicate rocks and limestone³. Cu, Zn, Pb and Ni are the main bound elements in the clinker⁴. The higher content of about the same set of heavy metals were encountered in the electrostatic precipitator dust which is in agreement with the earlier finding⁵. Cu, Cr and Zn contents are lower than those of the clinker, but Co and Cd concentrations are higher. It was found that finer particles are precipitated in electrostatic precipitators, the lower the CaO and SiO₂ contents the higher are the contents of K₂O and certain heavy metals. This suggests the probability of trace elements being carried out with fine particles of dust and gases.

In our earlier study⁶ on water-leach treatment of cement and electric filter dust samples, the trace metals were determined by polarographic and voltammetric techniques.

Experimental

Lithium tetraborate and lithium carbonate (Pharmacia Biotech, Sweden; A.R.) and HCl (AnalaR) and oxalic acid (ADWIC, A.R.) and standard solutions (100 mg/ml) of metal ions (A.R.) were used. Fusion mixture was prepared by mixing equal amounts of oxalic acid, lithium tetraborate and lithium carbonate. The samples of cement and other materials were obtained from Assiut Cement Company plant (Upper Egypt). The samples collected were average of 24 h work in the plant for 7 days. A Unicam SP 1900 atomic absorption spectrometer was used for the determination and comparing results were obtained using GBC 906 AA instrument.

Table 1. Average contents (minimum-maximum) of trace elements in cement and cement raw meals in ($\mu\text{g/g}$)^{*}

Metal	Clay	Limestone	Clinker	Gypsum	Cement	Dust	Slag
Cu	72.5–142.5	52.5–105.3	75.2–139.9	22.5–550.4	85.3–172.5	47.5–84.8	57.5–94.7
	(5.01)	(4.30)	(9.10)	(13.11)	(3.41)	(3.08)	(5.57)
Cr	505.1–607.5	49.7–70.3	222.5–342.5	n d	349.8–415.5	52.5–81.7	104.9–120.1
	(6.32)	(1.32)	(5.32)	–	(4.45)	(2.43)	(3.52)
Zn	140.1–169.8	122.5–180.1	165.1–299.7	95.2–134.7	192.1–349.9	162.5–170.2	72.5–150.3
	(3.39)	(3.10)	(4.72)	(4.51)	(6.03)	(5.06)	(2.81)
Pb	94.7–165.1	n d	230.2–267.5	n d	222.5–256.9	60.1–89.9	n d
	(6.82)	–	(5.43)	–	(7.31)	(3.32)	–
Ni	52.5–302.5	82.5–87.5	105.3–174.9	17.5–38.5	99.8–222.5	72.5–112.5	45.2–52.5
	(9.60)	(4.73)	(6.80)	(1.22)	(1.64)	(2.62)	(3.06)
Co	15.2–25.1	119.8–42.5	20.1–50.2	32.1–47.5	49.8–64.7	40.5–62.5	29.9–50.1
	(0.72)	(2.25)	(2.12)	(1.84)	(3.82)	4.06	(1.36)
Cd	5.01–7.5	20.1–21.9	12.5–17.5	n d	17.5–75.1	10.2–17.5	5.2–12.5
	(0.18)	(1.08)	(0.73)	–	(2.01)	(0.86)	(0.83)
Sr	n d	120.1–150.2	199.9–225.2	300.3–549.8	200.2–250.3	149.7–225.4	250.2–350.1
	–	(4.80)	(5.68)	(6.33)	(7.30)	(6.36)	(3.42)

*Values in parentheses are the standard deviation ($n = 3$) n d = not detected

Procedure The ground and dried samples (0.2 g) was mixed with fusion agent (0.8 g) in a platinum crucible and heated at 925–950^o) for 10 min. The resulting mass was cooled and dissolved in 1.88 M HCl-H₂O mixture (1.5, 120 ml). It was heated on a water-bath till the mass dissolved. The solution was then cooled and diluted to 500 ml with double-distilled water and analyzed by AAS.

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